

CAUSES OF PARTY POLARIZATION IN POST-COMMUNIST ALBANIA

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Abstract: Political parties are considered as important factors with regard to democratization and legitimacy of a political system. Post-communist ECE countries are characterized by researchers as manifesting weakly organized political parties, high voters' volatility and ideological uncertainty. A number of studies indicate, on the contrary, that post-communist political systems are also featuring a stable institutionalized party system. It is usually argued that a high level of party system institutionalization is a necessary condition or a prerequisite for democratization. This paper aims to investigate the conditions of party polarization in those political systems in which there is a stable and institutionalized party system. Theoretically speaking it is argued that low effective number of parties, low degree of voters' volatility and the stability among dominant parties constitute the main attributes of a highly institutionalized party system. The research question of the paper is: How to explain high party polarization given a relatively low effective number of parties in an institutionalized party system? The paper builds on the case study of Albania, which constitutes a deviant case contrary to the theoretical expectations. Contrary to a number of alternative theoretical explanations on the same issue, such as cultural explanations or those based on long-term causes as the nature of the dictatorial regime, this study present the following hypothesis: A change in the configuration of the social classes and ruling elites after 1992 together with the prevailing of a one dimensional dominant cleavage, opposite to a cross-cutting cleavage, in political competition brings about party polarization. The paper is based on the theoretical framework of Konrád and Szelényi (1979), and Eyal (2003) in order to identify the configuration of the postcommunist ruling elite as well as at the theoretical framework of (Dahl 1966) and (Casal Bërtoa 2014) concerning the formation of cumulative one dimensional cleavage opposite to the multidimensional and cross-cutting cleavage and their different effects. The paper is a qualitative research combined with process-tracing method in order to identify the critical juncture, the pertinent actors, the mobilization of cleavages and the discursive articulation of the political conflict. Political manifestos, main political speeches and party newspapers constitute the data of the paper.

Key words: institutionalized party system, party polarization, ruling elite configuration, one-dimensional cumulative cleavage

1. Introduction

Political parties have certain important functions in terms of providing legitimacy to the political regime, in channeling and articulating political representation and political division, as well as mitigating social conflict through institutionalized patterns and practices (Blondel, 1967; Lewis, 2001, p.546). Regime transitions and the uncertainty that characterize such periods (Schmitter, O'Donnell and Whitehead, 1986) pose a fertile ground as well as a challenge to the political scientists with regard to processes of party formation, re-alignment of political divisions, and the stability of the democratic regime. There is a shared normative understanding within students of party politics that links party system institutionalization with the consolidation of democracy. I argue in this paper that the prevailing normative dimension of party institutionalization concept precludes and limits a better understanding of the dynamics of and the interaction between party competition structure, cleavage formation and mobilization of political divisions in a post-authoritarian setting. Nonetheless, I do not dispute the partial positive effect, or the normative value of parties and party systems in being conducive to democracy (Kopstein, 2003; Hicken and Kuhonta, 2011, p.573).

This paper proposes a theoretical perspective that interweaves structural explanations with the strategies of pertinent political actors in the post-communist Albania. It posits to provide a different theoretical explanation from the theoretical frameworks that emphasize deep historical legacies or that prioritize cultural explanations in order to understand political conflict and party polarization (Krasniqi, 2008). On the other hand, the post-communist condition has been defined as manifesting a weak civil society and a delegitimized state (Howard, 2002; O'Dwyer, 2004, p.521). Initial theoretical propositions on party formation in post-communist East Central Europe

argued that: "...post-communist party system developments would differ considerably from those elsewhere in Europe because of weaker organizations and electoral bases" (Bekke and Sitter, 2005, p.245, Evans, 2006, p. 245). Acknowledging the role of the political elite as an agency of transformations and strategic choices (Elster, Offe and Preuss, 1998), this paper argues that proximate structural causes such as extrication from state socialist regime with the initial configuration of the social classes during the late socialist period, and the various social constituencies vying for dominance in the early years of post-communist party formation, (Eyal 2003; Higley and Pakulski, 1999) provide the theoretical frameworks for explaining the features of party system in post-communist Albania as well as modify to a certain extent the argument of weak party organizations and the assumed pervasive anti-party sentiment among the civil society. A distinction should be made between the absence of structured programmatic appeals or vague policies and the mobilization of a certain political division and cleavage that gives post-communist political parties certain identities (Grzymała-Busse, 2002, p.88).

The spatial model of party competition (Downs, 1957) emphasizes the ideological distance between parties in the ideological space. Two main features of a party system include party fractionalization and party polarization (Wang, 2014, p.688). It is assumed that an increase in the number of parties leads to party fractionalization and that it creates conditions for the spread of parties across the ideological space. On the other hand, a small number of parties, such as in a two-party system would lead to convergence towards the center, according to Downs' theory. However, party polarization is not causally linked with party fractionalization. "...high levels of polarization can be found in non-fragmented party systems (Pelizzo and Babones, 2007 in Wang, 2014, p. 688). The paper intends to provide a theoretical model that explains party polarization in

the case study of Albania, given the low level of electoral volatility, a stable and institutionalized party system and party-blocs.

2. Aims and Objectives

This study aims to provide a theoretical explanation of a persistent feature of a structured party competition in Albania, namely that of polarized party system. A principal aim of this exploratory work is to overcome prevailing cultural explanations that focus on the non-democratic identity of the political elite and that barely provide a causal mechanism of the effects of historical legacies, such as the absence of a democratic tradition, in instituting a polarized party competition. Nonetheless, this paper aims to rectify and modify the legacy and culturalist argument by delineating the dynamics of political elite configuration and the effect of the late socialist period in the mode of extrication from the past non-democratic regime. Thus, the emergence of the political conflict has to be understood as bounded in time and in context.

On the other hand, the paper strives to question the theoretical approach that analyzes the political and structured party competition based only on the interests and goals of the political elite. I contend that this perspective remains partial. At the same time, the normative underpinning of the party system institutionalization framework (Hicken and Kuhonta, 2011) and the classification of a post-communist regime as competitive authoritarian regime (Levitsky and Way, 2002; Higley and Pakulski, 1999, p.314-315), as in the case of Albania, does not provide a thorough explanation and it is restricted in time. It is for this reason that I include the time dimension, starting from the late state socialist period of the 1980s until the mid 1990s, as a

necessary analytical move in order to trace historical process of political dynamics, and to avoid the illusion of presentist, proximate explanations.

To this aim, this paper shall inquire into the existing social groups that were contending for primacy during the late state socialist period in the case of Albania. I argue that the essentialist nature of the communist regime, albeit the shared understanding of considering communist Albania a Stalinist regime, precludes the possibility to address the configurations, alliances and oppositions between the political and the cultural elite of the late period of state socialism. The trajectory and the public claims made by various social groups, such as the state socialist intelligentsia, technocrats, party bureaucracy and reformed communists during the late period of the communist regime shall help to actually explicate the legacy of the past regime. The paper looks at the political platforms, initial manifestos of the political opposition represented by the Democratic Party, and the ex-communist successor party, the Socialist Party. The parties are not taken as closed units, but as comprised of various competing internal fractions that bear different visions on the future democratic regime and transformation. Delineating the causal mechanism that links the emerging party formation in the transition stage with the mobilization of a particular political divide and cleavage in order to structure party competition in post-communist Albania, constitutes a proper way to substantiate the claims on party polarization. On the other hand, the paper takes into consideration possible alternative explanations that relate to institutional effects, such as the role of the electoral systems, or those that are related to a political learning process (Dawisha and Deets, 2006). More concretely, I scrutinize the changes or stability of the party system in Albania in time, by looking at the interaction between effective parties and party blocs (Bakke and Sitter, 2005), electoral volatility across parties and within

coalitions. Apart from that, the paper identifies the ideological distance and the discursive distance between the main political parties.

3. Research Question, Hypothesis and Methodology

The paper addresses the following research questions: How to explain high party polarization in a party system characterized by considerable party system institutionalization and low number of effective parties? This particular research questions stems from the puzzle of an assumed convergence or absence of ideological distance within the main effective parties in Albania, when considering the programmatic appeals historically. The feature of party polarization and the effective number of parties is related to the party system institutionalization which differs from party institutionalization per se. “In the party institutionalization literature there is a tendency to elide the issue of party institutionalization with that of party system institutionalization, the implication being that the institutionalization of a single party must contribute to the overall institutionalization of the party system...”(Randall and Svåsand, 2002, p.6). This paper considers, as Randall and Svåsand suggest, argues that the institutionalization of a party system has to be considered as a process in time (2002, p.14). Albeit I agree with the criticism to the spatial theory of party competition, that party polarization is not specific only to a fractionalized and multi-party system (Casal Bértoa, 2014, p. 22), still the reasons and causes of party polarization remain unexplained. The hypothesis that this paper posits to explain party polarization is formulated in this way:

H₁: The contingent configuration of particular social groups within the dominant factions of the party formations in a post-authoritarian setting mobilizes and entrenches a certain political cleavage (the regime divide) than party polarization increases.

This hypothesis is falsified in those cases when a different causal mechanism indicates a process at the micro-level of party organization with regard to political socialization and political learning that reinforces an existing political strategy of mobilizing the dominant cleavage. I borrow the concept of regime divide cleavage from Grzymała-Busse (see: Grzymała-Busse, 2002). A corollary of the first hypothesis relates to the counterfactual argument of a particular political elite configuration, which would structure the party system competition based on the economic cleavage.

H₂: An initial configuration of the political elite comprised of state socialist technocracy and state socialist intelligentsia, based on the constitutional consensus of a democratic polity and shared preliminary economic policies of transition would reinforce the economic cleavage and lower party polarization.

Initially, the political elite that comprised the ex-communist successor party, namely the Socialist Party, moved closer to the positions of the Democratic Party, with regard to the defense of human rights, the establishment of the rule of law, and of not reverting back to the pre-1945 social order (Biberaj, 2000; Fuga, 2008). Given that the initial Democratic Party's strategy with regard to the past was that of acknowledging the complicity of all the citizens under the past regime, initially the center-right party opposition did not mobilize the regime divide cleavage.

On the other hand, the trajectory and the position of the technocratic section of the state socialist ruling elite (Szelényi and Szelényi, 1995, 636) that dominated ideologically the Socialist Party compared to the party bureaucracy and the position and trajectory of the state socialist intelligentsia that dominated initially the Democratic Party restricts the possibility of mobilizing an exclusive cultural cleavage such as the regime divide cleavage. To some extent, I acknowledge the maverick mobilization of the regime divide cleavage by the center-right opposition political elite even if it was in contradiction with their social position in the political space.

The methodology used in this paper is based on case-study research across time in combination with process-tracing as a useful method to unravel the causal mechanism pertaining to the suggested theoretical model in order to understand the reasons behind party polarization in post-communist Albania. “The overall methodology of using causal-process observations in conjunction with generalizations can be called process-tracing” (Bennett 2006; 2008; George and Bennett 2005; George and McKeown 1985 in Mahoney 2012). Causal process observations are defined as: “observations on context, process, or mechanisms” (Brady and Collier 2010: 12). In the case study of Albania, the causal process observation include the interactions between the various social groups extricating from the state socialist regime involved in the process of party formation and the respective strategies employed in overcoming transition’s uncertainty. It is for this reason, that this paper considers party speeches, main newspaper articles that disseminate and articulate the positions of the competing groups, as sources of primary data to be analyzed as public discourse and texts.

4. Analysis and Interpretation of the Findings

At the advent of the emerging democratic regime in Albania the new political elite configuration was dominated by the cultural intelligentsia and the technocrats. The social category to comprise the elite of the democratic opposition was the intelligentsia of the state socialist regime. Most of the political elite of the main opposition party, the Democratic Party (PD), came from the cultural intelligentsia. These individuals possessed more cultural capital than political capital compared with the socialist technocratic reformers. The technocratic economic reformers sided with the close group of reformed communists presented by the ambivalent figure of the First Secretary of the Party. Initially within the democratic opposition there existed two fractions: one, the liberal intelligentsia, who was in defense of the rule of law, market reforms, and universal human rights, and the emerging conservative fraction comprised of traditional anti-communism, which was grouped into the new opposition party and anti-regime student movements (Biberaj, 2000). The social category of the traditional anti-communists comprised individuals coming from inter-war conservative parties and from the group of the politically persecuted under the state socialist regime. During the period 1990-1992, the category of anti-communist conservatives was not dominant in the opposition party. It is precisely at this time, that the former communists' discourse on democratic transition, their normative visions of the emergent democratic regime and the strategies to be pursued in dealing with the state socialist past, partly converge with the understandings, and the preferences of the dominant fraction of the democratic opposition.

It is important to scrutinize the changes happening within the state socialist regime during the 1980s in the communist bloc as well as in Albania, specifically. The particular focus on the configuration of the dominant social groups competing within the field of power of the state socialist regime, prior to regime transition is useful to understand later on the process of extrication of the social groups from state socialism and its effect on the formation of party system. Keneth Jowitt explains the internal transformation of the state socialist regime by indicating the change in the dominating social groups through time: “There is a marked change in the social base of the regime as well, with the more professional, skilled, and articulate strata increasing their status vis a vis the 'new class' of peasant-worker recruited officials”(1992, p.95). Other researchers of East Central Europe point out to the same processes: “Communist parties were thus pressured by the demands of an emerging middle class of professional and experts (e.g., Parkin 1971, Lipset and Dobson 1973, Konrad and Szelényi 1979, Strmiska 1987 quoted in Evans, 2006, p.247). Eyal (2003) makes a distinction between the positionality of the competing elites within the state socialist regime, namely between the official elite and the unofficial elite, which in most of the state socialist regimes in East Central Europe involved the dissidents and the cultural intelligentsia demoted from official positions.

In the case of Albania there is a recognition of the increasing role of the cultural intelligentsia and the technocracy in the process of legitimation of the past communist regime (Fuga, 2002). It should be noted that only in the last years of the state socialist regime, the leading heights of the regime in Albania provided some autonomous space or leverage to the cultural intelligentsia and the technocracy in comparison to the old guard or the party bureaucracy. Elez Biberaj claims that Alia started a process of Albanian style of glasnost that demanded open discussion of complaints and issues within the party and non-party associations officially controlled by the regime (1987).

“Alia, two and a half years after assuming power, has put his stamp on the country's politics, revised some of Hoxha's more radical policies and introduced small, but potentially significant innovations (Biberaj 1987, 480)”. These small but potentially significant innovations were introduced in the economic policies by demanding decentralized decision-making, and some allocation of private plots for peasants (1987). On the political dimension, two non-trivial steps of possible shifts and changes can be marked. These changes did not initiate an open process of political contestation nor relinquished the political monopoly of the Party. Nonetheless they indicated the realignments within the ruling elite and the configuration of the alliance between technical intelligentsia and the non-conservative fraction of the Party represented by Alia. It also indicated the emergence of a process of recognition by the regime of the autonomy of the cultural field, by granting more primacy to the state socialist intelligentsia (academics, university professors, researchers and associations) to speak more openly than before. “In these [Central Committee] and other senior mid-level appointments Alia has focused on experienced professionals with technical backgrounds (Biberaj 1987, 480)”. On the second step of open discussion on problems or concerns, members of the cultural field during the late 1980s, started to advocate and support the regime's style of 'glasnost'. It should be mentioned that the criticism indicated by the cultural intelligentsia, displayed not in unofficial samizdat journals but in official media of the regime, remained within the confines of the existing social order. The difference was that the cultural intelligentsia and the technocracy argued for a change in the legitimation formula of the past regime, by disavowing coercive rule. Nonetheless, I would like to point out that the post-socialist ruling elite of Albania can be classified, as Higley and Pakulski (1999) claim, as a fragmented political elite that was short of ‘diversity in unity’. In terms of elite circulation or elite reproduction, according to Higley and Pakulski: “One must also

ask if a circulation is shallow or deep- if elites are drawn from second-echelon (“deputy”) positions within existing political and social hierarchies and, thus, represent the established elite political and social type, or if many come from far down political and social hierarchies or even outside them (i.e., from exile, prison, or an underground movement) (1999, p.298). In the case of Albania, given the incremental increasing role of those fractions of the field of power, such as the intelligentsia and the technocracy in the late state socialist period of the regime, the post-socialist configuration of the political elite tends more towards reproduction rather than circulation.

I concentrate in the following part on the competing strategies and post-transition dominant elite configurations with effects on party formation and party polarization. The most criticized and inveighed social category either by the democratic opposition or the successor of the communist party was the bureaucratic fraction of state socialism (Szelényi 1995). The ex-communist party newspaper, *Zëri i Popullit* makes a clear distinction between experts, technocrats and privileged bureaucrats that hinder democratic reforms: “Above all, the (Labour Party) shall leave aside the shameful burden created by certain ex-leaders of the party that were corrupted and ignorant. Blaming the experts, that have a reputation in circles of expertise, would have been a total lack of realism and an offence to the new intellectual strata. Any extremist position leads to political gambling and adventure”(1991, June 6). Another more explicit criticism on the party bureaucracy is made evident by the regime’s newspaper: “Recently there have been a number of criticisms in *Zëri i Popullit*, that condemn the bureaucracy of the state apparatus and of the party, especially the privileges of some ex-functionaries of these apparatus”(1991, June 7). On the other hand, representatives of the liberal fraction of the Democratic Party reinstate the same castigation of the party and state bureaucracy: “The socialist

alternative is nowadays an ahistorical alternative because the Socialist Party is an alliance between reformist forces with liberal communists and communist (laborite) remnants, who are jeopardizing democracy”(Ceka, 1991, October 5). A similar diverse internal coalition in the opposition party was identified by Ceka himself: “Here [in the Democratic Party] there are intellectuals, workers, peasants, ex-politically persecuted, ex-communists, those expropriated and those who never became rich” (1991, October, 6). Henceforth, during the initial years of the democratic transition the prevailing fractions of the two opposing parties identified themselves in opposition towards the party apparatchiks and the inherited state bureaucracy of the past regime.

Representatives of the liberal and constitutional ideology in the Democratic Party delineate their strategy of a prospective structured party competition with the successor of the regime party. This strategy is based on a cross-cutting cleavage of unequal salience (Dahl 1966; Casal Bértoa, 2014, p. 22), whose balance tilts towards the economic cleavage rather than the cultural cleavage. The structuring of the future party competition, according to this fraction involves future-oriented rather than backward- oriented legitimation of the emerging democratic regime. “We are better prepared than the Socialist Party. We should show that we not only know which the main paths of development are but also that we should indicate the manners through which we shall attain these crucial components of democracy. When we discuss shock therapy or gradualism, this is not an issue of the way through which we shall transform the economy, but it is an issue of how to attack the remnants of the nomenklatura. We [the center-right opposition] think that the old nomenklatura [what used to be at the apex of the state socialist ruling elite] should be removed and dismantled immediately, whereas the socialists think that this should be done gradually” (Pashko, 1991, October, 12). Thus, there was a recognition that the party competition involves multi-dimensional political divisions. The liberal fraction of the democratic

opposition aims to mobilize the economic cleavage and not to accentuate the cultural cleavage. “We are a democratic party, with a clear democratic party program. Democracy means law, and equality of all citizens before the law” (1991, October, 12). Another representative of the liberal fraction argues against the mobilization of the regime divide (the communist vs. anti-communist cultural cleavage): “Anticommunism is necessary in Albania, but that should not lead us to civil war. We aspire to become European” (Rilindja Demokratike 1991). The dominance of the economic cleavage as determinant of the party competition in post-communist Albania was not heeded to. The liberal fraction, which later migrated to the civil society or to a new centrist party, did not manage to mobilize and entrench the economic cleavage, which according to Kitschelt (1999) would have led to a classical one-dimensional party competition and a more institutionalized party system that is less polarized.

The coalition of opposition parties including the Democratic Party, the Republican Party and the Social-democrats in the anticipatory parliamentary elections of 1992 obtained the majority of the seats in parliament, where the Democratic Party became the dominant party and could easily govern alone. The initial strategy of the opposition with regard to the past was reconciliation. With the removal and weakening of the liberal fraction of the Democratic Party, the traditional conservative and anti-communist fraction which had not been represented in government and came either from exile or from the lower social bases, became a crucial electoral constituency of the Democratic Party. It is at this particular stage when we witness a re-alignment of constituencies and political elites. The cultural cleavage that distinguishes between anti-communists and communists is mobilized. This particular political divide in the party competition pits different strategies of dealing with the communist past and increases the salience of memory politics in party competition. Cultural identities are sharpened and become

part of the political projects of opposing and polarized blocs. Borrowing from Peter Mair's conceptualization of cleavage formation, a cleavage is formed when: "when a particular social divide becomes associated with a particular set of values or identities which are made politically relevant by means of an organized party or group (Mair, 2006, p. 373, quoted in Casal Bértoa, 2014, p.17). Therefore, the political strategies of the ruling elite combined with re-alignments of the configurations of social groups in post-communist Albania have affected the party competition structure and the subsequent party polarization due to the nature of the cleavage (Kitschelt, 1992).

Throughout the post-transition period the party system in Albania has been dominated by two main parties, or two consistent blocs, to a large extent. The stability of the party system has been characterized by lower electoral volatility at least within the two blocs. On the other hand, it should be noted that the institutional effect of the electoral systems has not facilitated the entrance of new parties in parliament.

Conclusion

The post-communist transformation has perplexed and fascinated students of social change, regime transitions and East Central Europe. The uncertainty of societal and political processes had instigated theoretical explanations that were based on the assumed analogy between Western Europe and the post-communist countries predicated on the intended project of post-communist countries return to Europe. This project centered on transition to market economy and the consolidation of democracy. Political parties were identified initially as weak organizations having little or no bearing in the social divisions within the post-authoritarian settings, but mere run by a coterie of self-interested leaders.

This paper has tried to address through the case study of Albania the process of the entrenchment and reinforcement of party institutionalization and party competition based on a recurring party polarization. It has suggested a theoretical framework that combines a structural perspective with an agent-based strategic action of the political elite in order to provide the reasons for party polarization in post-communist Albania. At the same time, the paper has provided an alternative explanation towards the culturalist or deep historical legacies that seem to shape identities and cognitive frames. Contrary to the culturalist theoretical frame that barely identifies a causal mechanism to substantiate its explanatory and analytical claims, the perspective I have suggested avoids the pitfall of the assumed absence of democratic tradition or of political leaders committed to democracy. Nonetheless, a plausible theoretical framework that could dispute the suggested perspective by the author of this paper could be the social and

political learning frame, which identifies a different mechanism of the persistence of a political divide regardless of its initial emergence.

There has been a contentious debate within political science regarding the effect of the nature of a cleavage in party system institutionalization and on party polarization. The case study of Albania seems to prove the claim made by Kitschelt that the nature of a political divide and cleavage does matter in inciting or placating party polarization and inter party cooperation.

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